

Developing Composite Measures That Track Physical Activity Change In People With Early-Stage Parkinson's Disease Using Machine Learning And Wearable Sensors

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Introduction

Background. Wearable sensor-based digital measures allow objective and continuous monitoring of physical function and activity in people with early-stage Parkinson's disease (PD), and could be developed and validated as longitudinal disease progression markers.¹ Composite measures, based on the combination of individual digital measures, may capture multiple aspects of an individual's functioning comprehensively, while reducing noise.

Problem. There is limited agreement on appropriate methods for developing composite measures, such as the optimal selection of machine learning models, input features and approaches for model training.

Objective. To describe and evaluate two machine learning (ML) approaches to construct and optimize composite digital measures, based on the data collected from wearable sensors, that capture physical activity changes in people with early-stage PD:

- Supervised learning (reference-based), using standard clinical scores/patient-reported outcomes (PROs) as reference labels to train the model.
- Unsupervised learning (reference-free), without any training labels.

Methods

Device. The Verily Study Watch[®] (Verily Life Sciences LLC, South San Francisco, CA, USA; VSW) is a multi-sensor wrist-worn smartwatch that enables at home and in clinic passive data capture (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Verily Study Watch (VSW)[®].

*CAUTION Investigational device. Limited by Federal (or United States) law to investigational use.

Study Cohort. We collected at-home sensor data in the Personalized Parkinson Project (PPP; N=517),³ which we then split into separate train and test sets. Here, we focus on the train set (N=224; participants with early-stage PD, who enrolled within ≤ 4 years of diagnosis).

Table. Cohort demographic and clinical characteristics at time of enrollment		N=224
Mean age, yrs (SD)		61.5 (8.7)
Sex, n (%)	Male	137 (61.2)
	Female	87 (38.8)
Time from 1st symptom onset, yrs (SD)		2.1 (1.1)
Mean Hoehn and Yahr score (SD)		2.0 (0.5)
Mean MDS-UPDRS total scores (SD)	Part I	14.9 (7.6)
	Part II	8.4 (5.9)
	Part III	33.5 (12.9)
	Part IV	2.9 (3.2)
Mean PDQ-39 (SD)		32.1 (18.9)
Mean Schwab and England ADL (SD)		90.6 (9.0)

ADL = Activities of Daily Living; MDS-UPDRS = Movement Disorder Society-sponsored Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale; PDQ-39 = Parkinson's Disease Questionnaire - 39; SD = Standard Deviation

Overall Composite Measure Development and Evaluation. We define composite measure as a linear or non-linear combination of single measures (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Example of a composite measure, where w are the weights and b_0 is the constant term

$$\text{Composite measure} = w_1 \cdot \text{top cadence} + w_2 \cdot \text{bout duration} + w_3 \cdot \text{step counts} + b_0$$

Our models were trained on monthly-aggregated measures of walking and non-walking behavior previously developed from the VSW.⁵ **Nine walking and eight non-walking measures are used to generate composite measures.** The individual measures were selected among 42 measures, after removing highly correlated ones and taking those that cleared evaluation criteria on sensitivity and test-retest reliability.⁶

We evaluated two types of modeling approaches: (1) supervised learning (reference-based) approach; (2) unsupervised learning (reference-free) approach.

We evaluated the approaches (via cross-validation in the train set) using mixed-effect models to determine if the change of a composite measure was statistically significant using 2 year of data. Two-year effect sizes were calculated as standardized mean differences (Cohen's d). Monthly test-retest reliability of the measures were evaluated using intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs).

Conclusions and Next Steps

1. **Our results support the pursuit of sensor-based composite measures as potential tools to detect physical activity changes in people with early-stage PD.** Nine composite measures achieved higher Cohen's d than the clinical benchmarks, indicating that composite measures may capture physical activity changes associated with progression in a more sensitive manner than traditional clinical approaches.
2. **Unsupervised development of composite measures seems a promising approach.** Unsupervised measures can potentially mitigate limitation of inherent characteristics of training labels based on clinical scores (e.g., subjectiveness, low reliability). The unsupervised measures achieved similar Cohen's d as supervised composite measures. Unsupervised methods could generate composite measures comparable to composite measures generated from supervised methods.
3. **This work provides a foundation to utilize supervised and unsupervised ML techniques to build sensor-based composite measures using digital measures of walking and non-walking behavior.**
4. **Future research** will (1) explore different measure categories for composite measure generation, including sleep and autonomic measures, and (2) compare populations with/without PD to validate the composite measures for their ability to capture PD progression.

Development

Input

- 17 measures
- 9 walking
 - 8 non-walking

Learning

Our rationale to investigate two modeling approaches was to evaluate the potential of:

- A supervised learning strategy using traditional clinical labels, i.e., reference-based
- An unsupervised strategy (reference-free) that could mitigate any potential limitation or bias due to the inherent characteristics of training labels.

Supervised

Models: 5 ML algorithms (each trained using clinical scores/PROs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lasso regressor • Elasticnet regressor • Ridge regressor* • Gradient boosted regressor* • Random forest regressor* <p>* results omitted due to similar performance</p>
Labels: 5 different clinical scores/PROs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Total MDS-UPDRS Part III (excluding tremor, facial expression, and speech) B. Schwab and England ADL score C. MDS-UPDRS Part II + III, gait and posture score D. PDQ-39 and MDS-UPDRS II+III gait-only score E. PDQ-39 mobility score

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of the supervised approach

Unsupervised

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A principal component is a linear combination of measures that explains the most variance in the observed data. • Principal component analysis is commonly employed in situations with high correlation between measures. • Each principal component is evaluated here as an unsupervised composite measure, known as "PC j", where j is the jth principal component.
Autoencoder (AE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A non-linear modeling technique to learn latent representations of the input data. • Weights of the neural network are learned by minimizing the reconstruction loss between input and output through gradient descent. • Each hidden unit in the middle layer is a composite measure, defined as "AE i", where i is the index of the hidden unit.

Figure 5. Illustration of 2 principal component axes learned from the 2-dimensional measure input data. Principal components capture the most variance in the input data.

Figure 6. Illustration of a 5-layer autoencoder. The middle hidden layer (red), HL2, has two hidden units; the outputs of these hidden units are the composite measures.

Evaluation Results

Effect size (Absolute Cohen's d)

Results shown for top performing models, supervised (for each clinical score) and unsupervised. The models showed statistically significant changes over 2 years in mixed model analysis (FDR corrected p-value ≤ 0.05).

- Cohen's d values for most composite measures (>95% of the models evaluated) were higher than the clinical benchmark in year 1 and year 2, and the optimal composite measure (PC1) achieved a 2-year Cohen's d of 0.70 (benchmark clinical score: 0.42).
- Elasticnet trained using MDS-UPDRS part III is the best among the supervised composite measures.
- Unsupervised composite measures achieve Cohen's d performance similar to the supervised composite measures.

Supervised

Unsupervised

*Clinical benchmarks (modified MDS-UPDRS III)⁴: 2-years = 0.42; 1-year = 0.23

Test-retest reliability (ICC)

- All supervised and unsupervised composite measures achieve high month-to-month reliability (ICC>0.8).

Abbreviations
ADL = Activities of daily living
AE = Autoencoder
CI = Confidence interval
FDR = False discovery rate
ICC = Intraclass correlation coefficient
MDS-UPDRS = Movement disorder society-sponsored unified Parkinson's disease rating scale

PD = Parkinson's disease
PDQ-39 = Parkinson's disease questionnaire - 39
PRO = patient reported outcomes
PPP = Personalized Parkinson project
SD = Standard deviation
VSW = Verily study watch

References
1. Adams JL, et al. NPJ Parkinson's Disease. 2024;10(1):112.
2. Oyama G, et al. Scientific reports. 2023;13(1):3600.
3. Bloem BR, et al. BMC neurology. 2019 Dec;19:1-0.
4. Sotiriakis C, et al. NPJ Parkinson's Dis. 2023; 3(1):142.
5. Kowah N, et al. JMIR Hum Factors 2023;10:e48270.
6. Pagano G, et al. New England Journal of Medicine 2022; 387(5):421.

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KCH, CC, SS, SL, NK, ER, RK report employment and equity ownership in Verily Life Sciences.
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